

Sustainable SoluTions FOR
recycling of end-of-life Hydrogen
technologies

Deliverable D7.4

First Report on Dissemination and Communication
Activities

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Lead Contractor	ENVIPARK
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Prepared by	Marianna Franchino (ENVIPARK)
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Reviewed by	RINA, POLITO, ENVIPARK,

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Executive Summary

Main objective of this document is the identification and monitoring of the communication and dissemination activities undertaken by the BEST4Hy Consortium. The report refers to the period M1-18 and gives a framework of the current communication performances and stakeholders' engagement for further improvement of the communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy of BEST4Hy.

The project visual identity and the communication toolkit have been already reported in the overall strategy (Deliverable 7.3) and in the specific Deliverable 7.2. Then, this document is dedicated to the first dissemination phase focused on the four technologies development and its promotion among the researchers and scientific community.

1 Introduction to the project

BEST4Hy focuses on the development and validation of existing and novel recycling processes for two key fuel cell and hydrogen products: proton exchange membrane fuel cells (PEM FC) and solid oxide fuel cells (SOFC). The project aims to adapt two existing recycling processes already applied to other technologies and to validate a novel dismantling process for PEMFC. Furthermore, a novel SOFC recycling technology will be proved. At the end of the processes, the materials will be validated in terms of quality and performance when re-used in new components and in new stacks, demonstrating the overall efficiency of recycling. Ambitious targets for recycled content in new stacks/cells have been set and will be validated by fuel cell producers, to prove the viability of higher value, closed loop recycling. Environmental impact and cost-benefits evaluations on the proposed technologies will be performed. This will support a more efficient use of raw materials, including critical resources, and it will contribute to improve the end-of-life treatment of the hydrogen technologies and to foster a circular economy approach within the sector.

BEST4Hy international consortium is composed of industrial partners and research institutes: Environment Park SpA (Italy), CEA Liten (France), Turin Politecnico (Italy), Hensel Recycling GmbH (Germany), EKPO (Germany), Aktsiaselts Elcogen (Estonia), RINA Consulting SpA (Italy), University of Ljubljana (Slovenia).

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2 Communication and dissemination strategy management

The Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Action Plan (Deliverable 7.3) has been defined following a bottom-up approach and taking into consideration all partner's needs. This Consortium survey led to the definition of a multichannel approach strategy and KPI to monitor the performance along the project with the main objective to reach effectively stakeholders and maximize the project's results impacts.

The strategy is divided into 3 main phases according to the project's development. Currently, Phase I is ongoing:

- **Phase I (M1-M24)**, when the project **focuses on the technology selection and implementation of the four technologies**: the dissemination will be more oriented to maximize the scientific impact of the project, promoting the results amongst peers.
- **Phase II (M24-M36)**, when the project **focuses on the validation of results**, quality acceptance analysis and evaluation of the outputs for applicability, closed loop vs. open loop recycling. This phase will have a strong focus on disseminating the project's results once they are mature enough to clearly show the benefits of the technologies.
- **Phase III (M21-M36) focuses on** how to promote the results after the project for **the exploitation** through strategic assessment, analysis of the business case and replicability

3 Communication activities

3.1 Digital media

3.1.1 Website

A public website and social media are useful channels to disseminate and communicate about the results of a research project. These channels are fundamental to build a community interested in the project and are important requirements for a public co-financed research project. For BEST4Hy Project, a website with the following URL (<https://best4hy-project.eu/>) has been created (see Fig. 1). The website contains 8 sections (Home, Project and publications, Partners, News, Newsletter, Contact, Login) and it is regularly updated with news available for partners to translate in their native language to increase accessibility, as showed in the following pictures.

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Figure 1 BEST4Hy website homepage

Figure 2 BEST4Hy News section

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(January 2022, Italy): Dr. Sofia Saffirio, PhD student at Politecnico di Torino, presented its research work in the category *Materials and Technologies for H2 economy*.

Lab Scale Optimization Results on the 3 PEMFC Recycling Technologies Report – D1.1

The report describes the activities dedicated to the analysis of existing and novel recycling technologies for PEM fuel cells, crucial for the following steps on characterisation and evaluation of the recovered materials and their application in new cells and stacks manufacturing.

Analysis of Lanthanum and Cobalt Leaching Aimed at Effective Recycling Strategies of Solid Oxide Cells

BEST4Hy scientific paper published by the Polytechnic of Turin, dedicated to their research work on SOC (Solid Oxide Cells) recycling technology, specifically on Lanthanum and Cobalt leaching process for their recovery and recycling as critical raw materials in fuel cells' electrodes.

Alice Benedetto Mas, Silvia Fiore, Sonia Fiorilli, Federico Smeacetto, Massimo Santarelli, Ilaria Schiavi, Sustainability – MDPI

Figure 3 BEST4Hy Publication section

After one year of the project, the BEST4Hy website analytics show an average of 200 visitors/month (see Fig. 4) with direct source as main channels, included the referral (direct link from social media profiles for instance).

Traffic Analytics: Metrics Chart

best4hy-project.eu | All Devices | Worldwide | Last 12 months

Figure 4 BEST4Hy website visitors

In addition to the institutional website, partners websites are used. Below in Table 1, there are the partners' website with the estimated monthly visitors and the link to the news related to BEST4Hy on each partner's website.

Table 1 BEST4Hy Partners website

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Partner name	Partner website	Website visitors/month	News about the project in partners website (M1-18)
ENVIPARK	www.envipark.com	1500	https://www.envipark.com/en/progetti-p/21087-2/ https://www.envipark.com/en/envi-news-en/al-via-il-progetto-best4hy-per-il-recupero-dei-materiali-critici-rari-nelle-celle-a-combustibile/ https://www.envipark.com/en/envi-news-en/hydrogen-week-best4hy-project-awarded/ https://www.envipark.com/en/envi-news-en/hydrogen-stories-and-innovation-workshop/ https://www.envipark.com/en/envi-news-en/best4hy-h2020-project-stock-of-the-situation-after-one-year/ https://www.envipark.com/en/envi-news-en/best4hy-newsletter/ (Italian and English versions)
CEA	www.cea.fr	2300 for CEA Liten website	https://www.cea.fr/cea-tech/liten/english/Pages/Medias/News/Hydrogen-Vector/BEST4Hy-Project-AWARDED.aspx
POLITO	https://www.polito.it/ www.irisgroup.polito.it http://www.composit.es.polito.it/ http://www.steps.polito.it/ https://www.diatipolito.it/en/research/areas/environmental_sanitary_engineering	N/A	https://poliflash.polito.it/ricerca_e_innovazione/best4hy_recupero_e_riciclo_di_materiali_critici_da_tecnologie_e_dell_idrogeno https://poliflash.polito.it/awards/best4hy_premiato_come_best_success_story_2021_alla_eu_hydrogen_week
HRD	www.hensel-recycling.com	4.000	https://hensel-recycling.com/best4hy-h2020-projekt-wurde-gestartet/ sowie auf unserer LinkedIn Seite https://www.bvse.de/schrottelektronikgeraete-recycling/nachrichten-schrotteschrott-kfz/7749-best4hy-h2020-

This project has received funding from the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen 2 Joint Undertaking (now Clean Hydrogen Partnership) under Grant Agreement No 101007216.

[projekt-erste-ergebnisse-zu-neuen-recyclingprozessen.html](#)

EKPO	https://www.ekpo-fuelcell.com/	3100	https://www.ekpo-fuelcell.com/en/news/press-releases/eu-project-best4hy-receives-best-success-story-award
ELCOGEN	https://elcogen.com/	7250	https://elcogen.com/elcogens-participated-project-best4hy-wins-best-success-story /
RINA-C	www.rina.org	>1000	https://www.rina.org/it/media/CaseStudies/best4hy https://www.rina.org/en/media/news/2021/09/28/best4hy-project
UL	https://www.unilj.si/university	N/A	https://rcvt.si/2021/04/16/364/ https://www.fs.unilj.si/arhiv_sporocil/2021112908380288/

3.1.2 Social media

Social media are considered one of the most useful measures to disseminate projects updates and results, therefore a dedicated BEST4HyTwitter and LinkedIn profile (See Fig. 5 and 6) have been created.

To differentiate the type of contents shared and to benefit fully from the social media potential, some of the rules followed for the content strategy and social media management are listed below:

- Use meaningful # in order to be in the flow of the BEST4Hy topic related conversations. Some ideas (#CriticalRawMaterials, #rawmaterials #recycling, #hydrogen, #energy transition, , #research, #energy).
- Tag and connect with EU institutions, other EU-funded projects and notify the Project Officer of upcoming publications to maximise their visibility
- Try to engage the audience asking questions or using replies, retweets or tags.
- Dynamize the social media channels using different types of contents and diverse sources (text, pictures, videos, polls, links, etc.), for example:

1. Posts related to BEST4Hy's updates and news (presentation of partners, news about the publication of papers concerning project results, release of relevant project output, project progresses)

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2. Sharing of interesting insights related to project topics (research results and new technologies, relevant infographics)
3. Live posting during project events or when participating in thematic Conferences/Fairs.

Twitter and LinkedIn profiles are updated regularly with about two posts every week.

Figure 5 Example of BEST4Hy post on LinkedIn

Figure 6 Example of BEST4Hy post on Twitter

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In addition to the institutional project profiles, partner social media are used as a multiplier of BEST4Hy dissemination activities, as shown in Table 2:

Table 2 BEST4Hy social media accounts

Partner name	Social media profile	Social media profile followers	Post and repost about the project on partners social media profile
<i>TWITTER</i>			
PROJE CT ACCO UNT	@best4hy	42	- (average of 6 posts/month)
ENVIP ARK	@EnvironmentPark	560	https://twitter.com/EnvironmentPark/status/1451568955345317897 https://twitter.com/EnvironmentPark/status/1461297259333705730 https://twitter.com/EnvironmentPark/status/1486680243280781325 https://twitter.com/EnvironmentPark/status/1509520261581844480
CEA	@CEA_Official	39 400	
POLIT O	@PoliTOnews	18 700	
HRD	N/A		
EKPO	N/A		
ELCOG EN	@Elcogen_EU	850	
RINA-C	@RINA1861	2 500	https://twitter.com/RINA1861/status/1488085809572061184
UL	N/A		
<i>LINKEDIN</i>			
PROJE CT ACCO UNT	@ BEST4Hy Project	271	- (average of 6 posts/month)
ENVIP ARK	@Environment Park	3364	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6857333419198713856 https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6871410078478561280 https://www.linkedin.com/posts/environment-park_best4hy-h2020-project-stock-of-the-situation-activity-6915284911549489153-tYTE/?utm_source=linkedin_share&utm_medium=member_desktop_web
CEA	@CEA	173 000	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/cealiten_technologies-recovery-recycled-activity-6857278885441126401-0_f7

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	@CEA-Liten	8 100	
POLIT O	@Politecnico di Torino	168 000	
HRD	@Hensel Recycling	1 500	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6942504049934053376/
EKPO	@EKPO Fuel Cell Technologies GmbH	2 700	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ekpo-fuel-cell-technologies_eu-project-best4hy-receives-best-success-activity-6876150350454239234-LB59
ELCOG EN	@Elcogen	1 600	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/elcogen_best4hy-awarded-best4hy-activity-6872515749882212353-yh7Y
RINA	@RINA	225 000	
UL	University of Ljubljana	46 600	

The social media reached a high number of followers in this first year of project: 271 and 42 followers in LinkedIn and Twitter respectively. Considering the data related to the LinkedIn demographic, the followers are well distributed among the different sectors and job function: renewables, research and automotive (see Fig. 7); business development, engineering, research and operation (see Fig. 8).

Figure 7 LinkedIn followers by type of industry

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Figure 8 LinkedIn followers by type of job function

3.1.3 YouTube Channel

With the project underway, the BEST4Hy official YouTube channel has been opened (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCyBeBQS3Z7CoFs-pN8QPQmQ>) with the main objective to offer another opportunity of dissemination and a more in-depth explanations of the project activities through videos, which have been also found specifically useful during exposition and fair, resulting more attractive for stakeholders and attendees.

For the time being, the channel shares two videos related to the BEST4Hy project activities:

- **HYDROGEN STORIES AND INNOVATION - WS 9th February 22:** published in April 2022, it refers a short sum-up of the workshop with the Italian stakeholders realised in synergy with hydrogen related projects;
- **Manual dismantling process of a PEM fuel cell - Hensel Recycling in BEST4Hy:** published in March 2022, it is a video documentation of the research work for BEST4Hy project on PEM fuel cells manual dismantling process (first results at February 2022).

Figure 9 BEST4Hy youtube channel

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3.2 Newsletter and traditional media

Concerning newsletters and traditional media, every 6 months the BEST4Hy project gives an update of its development publishing a press release (see Fig. 10). The press release is shared within the Consortium, which is invited to publish the document through its institutional channels in English or their own language.

Figure 10 BEST4Hy press release

Since the beginning of the project, three BEST4Hy press releases have been produced. Environment Park, as WP leader of the dissemination, sent the BEST4Hy news to its community of newsletter subscribers (around 1 500):

ENERGIA SOLARE PER PRODURRE CARBURANTI ALTERNATIVI – INTERVISTA A SPOTLIGHT

Sfruttare l'energia solare per produrre carburanti puliti alternativi e contribuire al raggiungimento degli obiettivi europei di neutralità climatica. Sono questi gli obiettivi principali del progetto europeo **SPOTLIGHT**, dedicato allo **sviluppo e alla validazione di un dispositivo fotonico** per la conversione, alimentata dalla luce solare, di CO₂ e H₂ verde in **metano combustibile chimico e in monossido di carbonio** come materiale di partenza per la produzione del **metanolo**.

Nicole Meulendijks, TNO, coordinatrice del progetto **SPOTLIGHT**, è stata intervistata per la rivista AZOOptics, specializzata in campo ottico e fotonico. [Leggi tutto](#)

BEST4HY – PROCEDONO GLI STUDI SUL RICICLAGGIO DELLE CELLE A COMBUSTIBILE A IDROGENO

Risultati promettenti per il progetto europeo BEST4HY, finanziato dal programma Horizon2020 e lanciato da circa un anno. Il Consorzio, ben consolidato, prosegue con le sue attività di **ricerca sullo sviluppo e la validazione di tecnologie nuove ed esistenti per il riciclaggio di celle a combustibile di tipo PEM e SOC**, ottenendo ampia approvazione anche dalle organizzazioni che si sono unite all'**Advisory Board** di progetto.

Queste tecnologie ti appassionano? [Iscriviti alla newsletter di BEST4HY!](#)

[Leggi tutta la news.](#)

Figure 11 Screenshot of Envipark newsletter of April 2022

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3.2.1 BEST4Hy's Newsletter

Starting in the second project year of the project, the whole Consortium agreed to launch the BEST4Hy official newsletter: one newsletter every 6 months (April, October) with news and updates of the projects. ENVIPARK is in charge for the newsletter creation with the contribution of each partner in terms of contents and sharing of the final product.

First activities started in January with the website update through the registration form, pop-up and a specific section to collect newsletter subscribers (see Fig. 12, 13); meanwhile, emails have been sent to selected stakeholders directly and a social campaign has been started to collect subscribers (see Fig. 14, 15).

Structure of the BEST4Hy Newsletter:

News – BEST4Hy’s project updates. Generally, press release and updates on the main current activities, such as both PEM and SOFC activities development, LCA, regulation and so on.

Publications – last project publications in terms of scientific papers, posters, article etc.

Our suggestions – main current world news related to the hydrogen sector.

Figure 12 BEST4Hy newsletter pop-up

Figure 13 BEST4Hy newsletter registration form

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Figure 14 Newsletter promotion on LinkedIn

Figure 15 BEST4Hy's Newsletter news on ENVIPARK website

#1 BEST4Hy Newsletter – April 2022

Figure 16 #1 BEST4Hy Newsletter – April 2022

This project has received funding from the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen 2 Joint Undertaking (now Clean Hydrogen Partnership) under Grant Agreement No 101007216.

Analyzing the Newsletter contact list, it results a total number of 64 subscribers/recipients (30th April, 1st newsletter publication), where almost 50% are external contacts from different institutions and private companies and the other 50% are related to the partner’s institutions.

Among the recipients it is possible to identify the approximate number of people opened the newsletter email (readers) and from them the one who clicked directly to the news linked in the form and opened the news (clickers), as showed in Table 3:

Table 3 BEST4Hy Newsletter Analytics

NEWSLETTER	RECIPIENTS	READERS	CLICKERS
#1	64	27 (42%)	7 (11%)

3.3 EU acknowledgement

At the end of 2021, the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen 2 Joint Undertaking ceased operations and the Clean Hydrogen Partnership was creator as its successor. As project receiving funding from it, the communication materials with the funding programme information (logo and disclaimer mainly) have been updated.

The rules for the EU acknowledgment are still valid (D7.3) and here reported with the new Clean Hydrogen Partnership information:

All communication related to the project (including electronic communication, social media, etc...) and all infrastructures, equipment or major results funded under the grant must:

- display the EU emblem (*see Fig. 17*)
- include the following text: “This project has received funding from the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen 2 Joint Undertaking (now Clean Hydrogen Partnership) under Grant Agreement No 101007216. This Joint Undertaking receives support from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation program, Hydrogen Europe and Hydrogen Europe Research”.

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Figure 17 Clean Hydrogen Partnership and EU acknowledgment

4 Dissemination activities

4.1 Academic publications

Partners belonging to Research and public institution will publish papers based on project results and potentially published in international journals with high impact factor. A minimum target of 10 scientific publication has been set, while some of the papers will be published after the project conclusion. The academic dissemination will be coordinated by ENVIPARK. The content will be reviewed by the consortium's Scientific Committee (SC). The specified conditions for publication must be applied to the following formats: journal papers, book chapters, conference proceedings and peer-review publications.

At the present the consortium has submitted/published the following publication:

Table 4 BEST4Hy Scientific Publications

#	Partner	Journal	Title	Authors	Status
1	UL	MDPI: Sustain ability	Criticality and Life-Cycle Assessment of Materials Used in Fuel-Cell and Hydrogen Technologies	Mitja Mori, Rok Stropnik, Mihael Sekavčnik and Andrej Lotrič	Published (March 2021)
2	POLITO	MDPI: Sustain ability	Analysis of Lanthanum and Cobalt leaching aimed at effective recycling strategies of solid oxide cells	Alice Benedetto Mas, Silvia Fiore, Sonia Fiorilli, Federico Smeacetto, Massimo Santarelli, Ilaria Schiavi	Published (March 2022)
3	POLITO	ELSEVI ER: Sustain able Material s and Technol ogies	Hydrothermally-assisted recovery of Yttria-stabilized Zirconia (YSZ) from End-of-Life solid oxide cells		Under review

All the scientific papers are also available in the open access platform Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/101007216/?page=1&size=20>), where the BEST4Hy community has been created to share last publications of all type, from the publications in journal to the project's deliverables (see Fig. 18).

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Figure 18 BEST4Hy community in Zenodo

4.2 General articles

The Consortium is also involved in the dissemination activities with the publication of articles in specialized magazines focused to specific or wide target audience. Overall, 8 general articles are expected to be published during the project (almost one per each partner).

Until now, one general article has been published by Hensel Recycling in the *Hydrogen Standard journal* with a wide audience (see Table 5):

Table 5 BEST4Hy general article

#	Partner	Magazine	Title	Date of publication
1	HRD	<i>Hydrogen Standard journal</i>	<i>Closing the loop: the recycling of end-of-life fuel cells</i>	September 2021

4.3 Events

Table 6 BEST4Hy past dissemination events

Type	Partner	Title	When	Format
Web meeting	HRD	<i>e-mobil BW</i>	10/21	Online
Online event	ENVIPARK	<i>TechTalk: "R&I needs on Advanced Materials to unlock the hydrogen revolution"</i>	11/21	Online
Conference	POLITO	<i>XIII INSTM CONFERENCE</i>	01/22	<i>Sestriere (Turin, Italy)</i>

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Workshop	ELCOGEN	4th International Workshop on Degradation Issues of Fuel Cells and Electrolysers	05/22	Corfu (Greece)
Conference	POLITO	CORFU2022 - 9th International Conference on Sustainable Solid Waste Management	06/22	Hybrid
Conf&Expo	HRD	Hydrogen Technology Conference & Expo	06/22	Houston (Texas, USA)

During the project, all project partners are invited to participate and share their research activities within BEST4Hy and to present the project in conferences, fairs and workshops. Table 6 and 7 show the past events where the partners mentioned BEST4Hy and the future planned activities

Table 7 BEST4Hy future dissemination events

Type	Partner	Title	Planned date
Conference	POLITO	Pan American Ceramics Congress and Ferroelectrics Meeting of Americas (PACC-FMAs 2022)	July 2022
Conf&Expo	HRD	Carbon Capture Technology Expo Europe	October 2022
Fair&Expo	ENVI	ECOMONDO	November 2022

4.4 Workshops and trainings

For a better transferring of the results and expertise learnt, workshops and trainings have been planned along the project:

Table 8 BEST4Hy workshops and trainings planning

Month	Partner	Target
WORKSHOP		
M12	ENVIPARK	Interested SMEs
M18	FCH JU	LCA/LCC
M33	-	Standard and regulations (output: policy paper)
M36	HRD	Local authorities, AB members
TRAINING		
M33	ENVIPARK	
M36	HRD	

1st Workshop – Interested SMEs

The workshop has been held on February 2022 in online format and for the Italian stakeholders with the title “Storie di idrogeno e innovazione” (Hydrogen Stories and Innovation). ENVIPARK organised it in cooperation with other hydrogen related projects: EVERYWHERE, HyCARE and the H2IT, the Italian hydrogen and fuel cells association.

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Dealing with different topics on hydrogen technology, from their sustainability until their application to public events and the storage systems, the event reached around 60 attendees among academia, students and SMEs.

The workshop has been promoted on different communication channels of the project and of each partner, giving information materials even after the event on the BEST4Hy website and on its youtube channels with a short recap of the main discussions.

Figure 19 Post on the 1st BEST4Hy workshop

STORIE DI IDROGENO E INNOVAZIONE, the BEST4Hy workshop held on the 9th of February to Italian stakeholders turned out a successful event with a wide audience, composed by researchers and SMEs, to address specific hydrogen issues and lead a discussion among different figures.

After the initial presentations of progresses and results of the three projects – BEST4Hy, EVERYWHERE, HyCARE – and the Italian hydrogen association – H2IT, the workshop moved on an open discussion with all the attendees about the hydrogen related topics of environmental and social sustainability in all life cycle steps, security and storage systems, applications such as public events and construction site.

For the entire duration of the workshop, the attendees shared their ideas and thoughts on a digital platform that, as result, gave a **WORD CLOUD** from which the speakers had to start a cross-related

Figure 20 Summary of the 1st workshop on the website

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2nd Workshop – LCA/LCC

The second workshop has been planned for the next 09-10 November 2022.

It will be realized in the framework of *the International Conference and Expo on Recycling and Waste Management*, organised by the Global Scientific Forum.

Main topic of this workshop is to report the latest research results on sustainability of hydrogen fuel cells, considering their entire life cycle from the eco-design, to the recovery, recycling technologies for end-of-life (EoL) PEM/SOFC fuel cells and to the life cycle sustainability assessment with a general overview on worldwide regulations and standards. Title of the workshop will be “Circularity in Hydrogen Fuel Cells – technologies and current regulation for the EoL of fuel cells and recycled material valorisation”.

More project partners have been involved in this event: CEA and POLITO for the research activities on the PEM/SOFC fuel cells explanations, UL for the LCA/LCC studies and ENVI for the regulation’s aspects. The main organisers are ENVIPARK and IMDEA, coordinator of the BEST4Hy sister projects eGHOST, SH2E.

5 Evaluation and monitoring of communications and dissemination activities

WP 8 leader monitors and reports continuously about communication and dissemination activities, while all partners indicate specific initiatives undertaken to track them. To benchmark impacts and results, here below are listed some targets and achievements of the first period.

Table 9 Monitoring KPI

Channel	Goal	Status at M18
Traditional media	8 general articles	1
Scientific publications	10 papers	3
BEST4Hy social media	300 Twitter and LinkedIn followers	42 Twitter + 271 LinkedIn
BEST4Hy website	400 visitors/month	200

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